

Active Tree of Life WikiProjects and Recommended structure for articles

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[WikiProject Tree of Life](#)

This WikiProject gives links to all active and inactive WikiProjects which may be of interest to editors of species articles. I've included the following active WikiProjects which may be of interest to the NZ species editathon attendees:

[WikiProject Plants](#)

Plant article structure

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:WikiProject_Plants/Resources#Article_structure

Recommends looking at Featured Articles (see below)

Featured Article (highest quality Wikipedia articles) for WikiProject plants

<https://wp1.openzim.org/#/project/Plant/articles?quality=FA-Class>

[WikiProject Fungi](#)

Fungi article structure

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:WikiProject_Fungi#Article_structure

Featured Articles for WikiProject Fungi

<https://wp1.openzim.org/#/project/Fungi/articles?quality=FA-Class>

[WikiProject Fungi/Lichen task force](#)

Lichen article structure

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:WikiProject_Fungi/Lichen_task_force/Article_template

Featured Articles for Lichen article structure

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:WikiProject_Fungi/Lichen_task_force/Popular_pages
in particular [Lobaria pulmonaria](#) and [Parmotrema perlatum](#).

[WikiProject Algae](#)

Algae article structure Can't find specific advice

Featured Articles for Algae. There are no Algae species articles that have been classified as a FA. Some Good Article quality species articles can be found here

<https://wp1.openzim.org/#/project/Algae/articles?quality=GA-Class> particularly *Postelsia* and *Rapaza*.

[WikiProject Arthropods](#)

Arthropod article structure

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:WikiProject_Arthropods#Article_contents

Featured Articles for WikiProject Arthropods. There are no Arthropod species articles that have been classified as a FA. Some Good Article quality species articles can be found here

<https://wp1.openzim.org/#/project/Arthropods/articles?quality=GA-Class>

[WikiProject Insects](#)

Insect article structure

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:WikiProject_Insects#Article_contents

Featured Articles for WikiProject insects

<https://wp1.openzim.org/#/project/Insects/articles?quality=FA-Class>

[WikiProject Insects/Ant task force](#)

Ant article structure - can't find specific advice

Featured Articles for Ant task force

https://wp1.openzim.org/#/project/Ant_task_force/articles?quality=FA-Class

[WikiProject Insects/Hymenoptera task force](#)

Hymenoptera article structure - can't find specific advice

Featured Articles for WikiProject Hymenopter. There are no hymenoptera species articles that have been classified as a FA. Some Good Article quality species articles can be found here

<https://wp1.openzim.org/#/project/Hymenoptera/articles?quality=GA-Class>

[WikiProject Beetles](#)

Beetle article structure https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:WikiProject_Beetles/Layout

Featured Articles for WikiProject Beetles. There are no beetle species articles that have been classified as a FA. Some Good Article quality species articles can be found here

<https://wp1.openzim.org/#/project/Beetle/articles?quality=GA-Class>

[WikiProject Diptera](#)

Diptera article structure

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:WikiProject_Diptera/Article_formats

Featured Articles for WikiProject Diptera. There are no diptera species articles that have been classified as a FA. Some Good Article quality species articles can be found here

<https://wp1.openzim.org/#/project/Diptera/articles?quality=GA-Class>

[WikiProject Lepidoptera](#)

Lepidoptera https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:WikiProject_Lepidoptera/Article_formats

Featured Articles for WikiProject Lepidoptera

<https://wp1.openzim.org/#/project/Lepidoptera/articles?quality=FA-Class>

[WikiProject Spiders](#)

Spider article structure

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:WikiProject_Spiders/Article_formats

Featured Articles for WikiProject Spiders

<https://wp1.openzim.org/#/project/Spiders/articles?quality=FA-Class>

[WikiProject Fishes](#)

Fish article structure

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:WikiProject_Fishes#Article_format

Featured Articles for WikiProject Fishes

<https://wp1.openzim.org/#/project/Fishes/articles?quality=FA-Class>

[WikiProject Gastropods](#)

Gastropod article structure

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:WikiProject_Gastropods/Article_contents

Featured Articles for WikiProject Gastropods

<https://wp1.openzim.org/#/project/Gastropods/articles?quality=FA-Class>

[WikiProject Bivalves](#)

Bivalve article structure

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:WikiProject_Bivalves#Article_contents

Featured Articles for WikiProject Bivalve. There are no bivalve species articles that have been classified as a FA. Some Good Article quality species articles can be found here

<https://wp1.openzim.org/#/project/Bivalves/articles?quality=GA-Class>

[WikiProject Amphibians and Reptiles](#)

Amphibian and Reptile article structure

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:WikiProject_Amphibians_and_Reptiles#Article_contents

Featured Articles for WikiProject Amphibians and Reptiles

https://wp1.openzim.org/#/project/Amphibian_and_reptile/articles?quality=FA-Class

[WikiProject Birds](#)

Bird article structure: Guidelines for layout of bird articles section of

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:WikiProject_Birds

Featured Articles for WikiProject Birds

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:WikiProject_Birds/Showcase

[WikiProject Mammals](#)

Mammal article structure - can't find specific advice

Featured Articles for WikiProject Mammals

<https://wp1.openzim.org/#/project/Mammal/articles?quality=FA-Class>

[WikiProject Protista](#)

Protista article structure

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:WikiProject_Protista#Article_design

Featured Articles for WikiProject Protista. Can't find Featured Articles

Classification of Articles

Wikipedia articles are classified from Stub to Featured Article depending on how complete the article is. Below is the English Wikipedia assessment table giving a quality and importance assessment for applicable English Wikipedia articles as at June 2024.

All rated articles by quality and importance						
Quality	Importance					Total
	Top	High	Mid	Low	???	
★ FA	1,562	2,464	2,382	1,896	180	8,484
★ FL	179	667	762	700	106	2,414
ⓘ A	360	680	786	579	83	2,488
⊕ GA	3,180	7,217	14,562	19,093	1,734	45,786
B	16,646	32,340	53,380	66,330	20,997	189,693
C	16,621	53,351	133,083	299,487	85,459	588,001
Start	18,449	91,958	412,517	1,586,521	398,413	2,507,858
Stub	4,212	31,620	278,052	2,780,170	760,723	3,854,777
List	4,784	16,908	53,189	189,210	66,933	331,024
Assessed	65,993	237,205	948,713	4,943,986	1,334,628	7,530,525
Unassessed	125	499	1,265	18,974	430,309	451,172
Total	66,118	237,704	949,978	4,962,960	1,764,937	7,981,697

English Wikipedia assessment table. A [screenshot of the English Wikipedia assessment table](#) (as at June 2024) by Halfak (WMF), [CC BY-SA 4.0](#), via Wikimedia Commons

Approximately 48% of applicable articles on English Wikipedia are classified as being stub articles.

Often WikiProjects have an article quality and importance assessment table that applies to articles that fall within the purview of that WikiProject. For example below is the [WikiProject New Zealand assessment table](#) giving a quality and importance assessment for New Zealand related Wikipedia articles as at September 2024.

New Zealand articles by quality and importance							
Quality	Importance						
	Top	High	Mid	Low	NA	???	Total
★ FA	<u>1</u>	<u>12</u>	<u>16</u>	<u>27</u>			<u>56</u>
★ FL		<u>1</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>16</u>			<u>19</u>
ⓘ A		<u>1</u>	<u>11</u>	<u>22</u>			<u>34</u>
⊕ GA	<u>10</u>	<u>18</u>	<u>60</u>	<u>232</u>			<u>320</u>
B	<u>66</u>	<u>154</u>	<u>293</u>	<u>891</u>			<u>1,404</u>
C	<u>87</u>	<u>355</u>	<u>1,247</u>	<u>4,591</u>			<u>6,280</u>
Start	<u>3</u>	<u>297</u>	<u>2,242</u>	<u>17,610</u>			<u>20,152</u>
Stub			<u>724</u>	<u>25,427</u>		<u>1</u>	<u>26,152</u>
List	<u>3</u>	<u>44</u>	<u>328</u>	<u>1,960</u>			<u>2,335</u>

New Zealand articles assessment table. A [screenshot of WikiProject New Zealand assessment table](#) (as at September 2024) Wikimedia Foundation [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

Of those applicable articles that fall within WikiProject New Zealand, approximately 45% are classified as stub articles. One of the most impactful contributions Wikipedia editors can make is to improve the quality of existing stub articles.

Examples of stub to C class quality articles

The following examples show what a typical stub, start and C class species article might look like.

Stub Class Article Example

Ataxocerithium huttoni

6 languages ▼

Article Talk

Read Edit View history Tools ▼

From Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia

Ataxocerithium huttoni is a species of medium-sized sea snail, a marine gastropod mollusc in the family Cerithiidae.

References [edit]

Further reading [edit]

- Powell A W B, William Collins Publishers Ltd, Auckland 1979 ISBN 0-00-216906-1

<i>Ataxocerithium huttoni</i>	
Scientific classification	
Kingdom:	Animalia
Phylum:	Mollusca
Class:	Gastropoda
(unranked):	clade
	Caenogastropoda
	clade Sorbeoconcha
Superfamily:	Cerithioidea
Family:	Cerithiidae
Genus:	<i>Ataxocerithium</i>
Species:	<i>A. huttoni</i>
Binomial name	
<i>Ataxocerithium huttoni</i> <div>(Cossmann, 1895)</div>	
Synonyms	
<i>Cerithium cancellatum</i> Hutton, 1873	
<i>Colina huttoni</i> Cossmann, 1895	
<i>Cerithium invaricosum</i> Odhner, 1924	

Taxon identifiers

Ataxocerithium huttoni

Wikidata: Q3139682 · GBIF: 2301874 · iNaturalist: 386270 · IRMNG: 10051194 · NZOR: 708598f6-c7a1-4f00-b88f-4f08d3c6d94f · OBIS: 592487 · WoRMS: 592487

This Cerithiidae-related article is a stub. You can help Wikipedia by expanding it.

Categories: Cerithiidae | Gastropods of New Zealand | Gastropods described in 1895 | Cerithiidae stubs

Screenshot of [Ataxocerithium huttoni](#) English Wikipedia article (as at 19 September 2024). Wikimedia Foundation [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

Start Class Article Example

Eatoniella notalabia

4 languages ▼

Article Talk

Read Edit View history Tools ▼

From Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia

Eatoniella notalabia is a species of marine gastropod mollusc in the family Eatoniellidae.^[1] It was first described by Winston F. Ponder in 1965. It is endemic to the waters of New Zealand.

Description [edit]

Eatoniella notalabia has a minute ovate-conical shell, with a swollen body whorl. Colour of the species' shells can vary from yellow-brown, purplish-brown to black.^[2] The species measures 1.26mm by 0.8mm.^[3] The animal itself is white-coloured with a narrow strip of black.^[2] Specimens collected from Piha in the 1960s were uniformly white, with no black.^[2]

Distribution [edit]

The species is Endemic to New Zealand.^[1] The holotype was collected by Ponder himself on 1 January 1964, at Goat Island Bay (modern-day Cape Rodney-Okakari Point Marine Reserve) in the Auckland Region.^[4] The species is found in the waters of the North Island, South Island, Auckland Islands and the Chatham Islands, and is particularly abundant in the South Island and Stewart Island.^[2]

The species is found on algae/seaweeds at low tide.^{[2][5]}

References [edit]

- ↑ ^{*a b*} Bieler R, Bouchet P, Gofas S, Marshall B, Rosenberg G, La Perna R, Neubauer TA, Sartori AF, Schneider S, Vos C, ter Poorten JJ, Taylor J, Dijkstra H, Finn J, Bank R, Neubert E, Moretzsohn F, Faber M, Houart R, Picton B, Garcia-Alvarez O, eds. (2022). "*Eatoniella notalabia* Ponder, 1965". *MolluscaBase. World Register of Marine Species*. Retrieved 15 November 2022.
- ↑ ^{*a b c d e*} Ponder, W. F. (1965). "The Family Eatoniellidae in New Zealand". *Records of the Auckland Institute and Museum*. **6**: 47–99. ISSN 0067-0464. JSTOR 42906115. Wikidata Q58676802.
- ↑ "*Eatoniella notalabia*". *New Zealand Mollusca*. Retrieved 20 November 2022.
- ↑ Blom, Wilma M. (2020). "Fossil and Recent molluscan types in the Auckland War Memorial Museum. Part 4: Gastropoda (Caenogastropoda - Neocyclotidae to Epitoniidae). [Cyclophoroidea, Cerithioidea, Littorinimorpha]". *Records of the Auckland Museum*. **55**: 101–150. doi:10.32912/RAM.2020.55.7. ISSN 1174-9202. JSTOR 27008995. S2CID 229670783. Wikidata Q106828489.
- ↑ Hayward, Bruce; Morley, Margaret (2004). "Intertidal Life Around the Coast of the Waitakere Ranges, Auckland" (PDF). Auckland Regional Council. Retrieved 17 November 2022.

Eatoniella notalabia

Holotype of *Eatoniella notalabia* from Auckland War Memorial Museum

Scientific classification ✎

Domain: Eukaryota

Kingdom: Animalia

Phylum: Mollusca

Class: Gastropoda

Subclass: Caenogastropoda

Order: Littorinimorpha

Family: Eatoniellidae

Genus: *Eatoniella*

Species: ***E. notalabia***

Binomial name

Eatoniella notalabia
(Ponder, 1965)

Synonyms

- *Eatoniella (Dardaniopsis) notalabia* (Ponder, 1965)
- *Eatoniella (Eatoniella) notalabia* (Ponder, 1965)

Taxon identifiers	
<i>Eatoniella notalabia</i>	Wikidata: Q6783371 · CoL: 38BXY · EoL: 15764654 · GBIF: 2300859 · iNaturalist: 409818 · IRMNG: 10084525 · NZOR: 5e13dd77-47b9-4859-a97d-477d49f14d3a · OBIS: 598448 · Open Tree of Life: 2894246 · WoRMS: 598448

Categories: Eatoniellidae | Gastropods described in 1965 | Gastropods of New Zealand | Endemic fauna of New Zealand | Endemic molluscs of New Zealand | Molluscs of the Pacific Ocean | Taxa named by Winston Ponder

Screenshot of *Eatoniella notalabia* English Wikipedia article (as at 19 September 2024). Wikimedia Foundation [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

C Class Article Example

Peraxilla colensoi

4 languages ▼

Article Talk

Read Edit View history Tools ▼

From Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia

Peraxilla colensoi, the **scarlet mistletoe**, is a shrubby parasitic plant composed of broad, leathery leaves that grow up to 8 cm long and have a red edge. The common name is derived from the scarlet petals of the plant that bloom every October to January. These mistletoes are parasitic plants whose seeds attach themselves to host plants. The most common host for these plants is the **silver beech**. The plant can grow up to 3 meters tall and are often located in low altitudes throughout the North and South Islands of New Zealand.

Description [edit]

This is a parasitic plant and relies on its host to grow and survive on. Individuals of this species are shrubs up to 3m long and will further out to branches on its host. It has glossy green paired leaves and red tubular flowers. The fruit produced is a small, round yellow color and the leathery leaves of the shrub will fall and cover the forest floor.^[1]

Distribution [edit]

Peraxilla colensoi naturally occurs to grow on other trees in New Zealand. It is native to the North and South Island of New Zealand. Specifically it can be found on the South Island beech forests. This is a parasitic plant therefore it grows on other trees, plants, and flowers from October to January. The abundance of *Peraxilla colensoi* appears to follow a structural gradient in forests. Forests that contain open-canopied, all-aged forests had higher densities of *peraxilla colensoi*, while a dense-canopied, even-aged forest contained little to no *Peraxilla*.^[2] The position of this mistletoe is likely dependent on the opportunities available for seed dispersing birds to excrete and regurgitate seeds.^[2] This indicates that different forest structures can present different opportunities for birds which impacts mistletoe establishment. *Peraxilla* is likely to be most common in areas that observe frequent bird appearances. Several studies have observed larger host trees had a higher rate of *peraxilla* in comparison to smaller host trees.^[2] The correlation between tree size and mistletoe abundance is that larger trees are able to receive a higher number of mistletoe seeds since they are better perches for birds, resulting in the positive relationship between tree size and mistletoe abundance.

Habitat and ecology [edit]

The species is an annual short-lived plant that flowers between the months October through January. Temperatures during this time could be as low as 68 degrees fahrenheit to a high of 86 degrees fahrenheit. This is a parasitic plant, so it latches onto other species to grow, therefore interacting with other species. It relies on its host species for nutrients and water. It can be found in the mid elevation points on trees.^[3]

Flowers and fruit [edit]

Flowers of *Peraxilla colensoi* are red and orange in color. They usually flower in the months of October to January. The flowers grow in groups, and are usually found in clumps of 3 to 10. The flower heads usually grow up to 60 mm long. The buds of the flower are not able to open up by themselves. They require assistance from birds that try to extract the nectar from the flower. They twist on the top of the flower that allows it to open up and this helps the birds get nectar while also allowing the flower fertilize as well. The flowers are able to fall and litter the entire floor below them.^[1]

Peraxilla colensoi

Herbarium specimen

Scientific classification [edit]

Kingdom: **Plantae**

Clade: **Tracheophytes**

Clade: **Angiosperms**

Clade: **Eudicots**

Order: **Santales**

Family: **Loranthaceae**

Genus: ***Peraxilla***

Species: ***P. colensoi***

Binomial name

Peraxilla colensoi

William Colenso

In full bloom

Peraxilla colensoi also has fruits that grow to be small and oval shaped and are a yellowish golden color when they ripen. These fruits are eaten by the birds in the area and the seeds of the fruit are excreted by the bird. This allows the plant to spread to new locations. In order for the seed to develop it must land on a branch so it can attach with its haustoria, which are sucker like roots. The preferred host species for this parasitic species is *Lophozonia menziesii* but there are 16 other species that are known to be host species for *Peraxilla colensoi*.^[1]

Predators and seed dispersers [[edit](#)]

Peraxilla colensoi is browsed by the **common brushtail possum**, an invasive species in New Zealand. The increase in browsing by this animal has caused a great depletion in the plant species, leading to it possibly being endangered.^[1]

The caterpillar of the **endemic** moth *Zelleria maculata* mines the leaves as well as feeds on the inside flower buds of *P. colensoi* and as a result can affect the production of seeds of this plant.^{[4][5][6]}

Since *Peraxilla colensoi* is a parasitic plant its seeds attach itself to its preferred host as a source of food, with its most common host being silver beeches.^[7] The fruit of the plant when ripe is eaten by birds. These birds excrete these seeds which hopefully will land on a branch and attach through its adaptive sucker roots known as haustoria.^[8]

References [[edit](#)]

- [^] ^a ^b ^c ^d "Peraxilla colensoi" . *New Zealand Plant Conservation Network*. Retrieved 2020-11-02.
- [^] ^a ^b ^c Norton, David A.; Ladley, Jenny J.; Owen, Hamish J. (September 1997). "Distribution and population structure of the loranthaceous mistletoes *Alepis flavida*, *Peraxilla colensoi*, and *Peraxilla tetrapetala* within two New Zealand *Nothofagus* forests" . *New Zealand Journal of Botany*. **35** (3): 323–336. doi:10.1080/0028825X.1997.10410158 . ISSN 0028-825X .
- [^] Sessions, L. A.; Kelly, D. (2001). "Methods for monitoring herbivory and growth of New Zealand mistletoes (Loranthaceae)" . *New Zealand Journal of Ecology*. **25** (2): 19–26. JSTOR 24055294 .
- [^] Dave Kelly; Jenny J. Ladley; Alastair W. Robertson; Lisa Crowfoot (8 October 2008). "Flower predation by *Zelleria maculata* (Lepidoptera) on *Peraxilla* mistletoes: effects of latitude and fragmentation, and impact on fruit set" (PDF). *New Zealand Journal of Ecology*. **32** (2). Retrieved 15 January 2017.
- [^] Dave Kelly; Jenny J. Ladley; Alastair W. Robertson; David A. Norton (2000). "Limited forest fragmentation improves reproduction in the declining New Zealand mistletoe *Peraxilla tetrapetala* (Loranthaceae)". In Andrew G. Young; Geoffrey M. Clarke (eds.). *Genetics, Demography and Viability of Fragmented Populations* . Cambridge University Press. p. 241 –252. doi:10.1017/CBO9780511623448.018 . ISBN 0521794218 .
- [^] Peter de Lange; David Norton, eds. (June 1997), *New Zealand's loranthaceous mistletoes* (PDF), pp. 1–225, Wikidata Q124157540, archived from the original (PDF) on 6 January 2024
- [^] J. de Lange, Peter (20 July 1995). "Historical Distributions of the New Zealand's loranthaceous mistletoes". *Department of Conservation*: 17–20.
- [^] "Peraxilla colensoi Scarlet Mistletoe" . *Art and Science of Horticulture*. Retrieved 2020-11-02.

Taxon identifiers	
<i>Peraxilla colensoi</i>	Wikidata: Q15382281 · Wikispecies: Peraxilla colensoi · CoL: 77434 · GBIF: 4002232 · iNaturalist: 366707 · IPNI: 550672-1 · NCBI: 1288323 · NZOR: 66e225d5-92d1-4a16-80ce-c72dfe6b80e7 · NZPCN: 191 · Observation.org: 331895 · Open Tree of Life: 6040923 · Plant List: tro-100356123 · POWO: urn:lsid:ipni.org:names:550672-1 · Tropicos: 100356123 · WFO: wfo-0001035748
<i>Loranthus colensoi</i>	Wikidata: Q39193971 · CoL: 3W5P7 · GBIF: 5640294 · IPNI: 549245-1 · NZOR: fd0c7c97-75ed-4089-8473-d6da7e8a5680 · POWO: urn:lsid:ipni.org:names:549245-1 · Tropicos: 100356122 · WFO: wfo-0001035747

Categories: [Loranthaceae](#) | [Flora of New Zealand](#)

Screenshots of *Peraxilla colensoi* English Wikipedia article (as at 19 September 2024) . Wikimedia Foundation [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)